

Integrated Hydrogeological Characterization of Rugged Terrains: A Case Study of the Bhatti Mine Area

Ravindra Pratap Singh* Nirmala R** Jitendra Kumar Dixit***

ABSTRACT

This proposed research aims to comprehensively investigate the hydrogeological dynamics of rugged terrains, focusing on the Bhatti Mine area as a case study. The study will employ an integrated approach that combines Double-Ring Infiltrometer Tests and Vertical Electrical Sounding surveys to analyze infiltration behaviour and subsurface properties. The research will address the intricate interplay between surface conditions, vegetation, and geological features in shaping hydrological patterns. The study seeks to enhance our understanding of water movement, absorption, and percolation in such challenging terrains, contributing to improved environmental assessments and land management strategies.

This research will contribute to advancing our understanding of hydrogeological dynamics in rugged terrains, shedding light on the complex interactions between surface conditions, vegetation, and geological features. The integrated approach will provide valuable insights for groundwater management, environmental assessments, and land management strategies in similar challenging landscapes. By addressing the limitations and challenges associated with data collection in rugged terrains, the study will also offer innovative solutions for conducting field research in difficult-to-access areas.

Keywords: infiltration behaviour, Double-Ring Infiltrometer Tests, Vertical Electrical Sounding, hydrological assessment, land management.

INTRODUCTION

Delhi, historically referred to as Inderprastha holds a pivotal role in the rapidly advancing economy. Its evolution from ancient times to a contemporary urban centre has been fuelled by swift urbanization and burgeoning industrialization. This transformation has triggered a surge in population growth, rendering Delhi the most densely populated city in India, with a density of 11,297 persons per square kilometre as recorded in the 2011 Census. This population upsurge has exerted immense pressure on natural resources, particularly the vital resource of drinking water. However, the available surface water sources are proving inadequate to satiate this growing thirst, leading to an intensified reliance on groundwater.

Recent research underscores a disconcerting trend the city's escalating dependence on groundwater is outpacing its capacity for replenishment. This valuable resource is facing a dual threat of depletion and contamination, a

phenomenon acutely exacerbated in the National Capital Region due to escalating demand and the influx of pollutants from various industries (Dutta et al. 1996; Dutta 2005). Amid these challenges, a glimmer of hope persists: sustainable groundwater usage is contingent upon effective replenishment mechanisms using untainted water sources. However, the urban landscape in Delhi introduces further complications, including urban flooding and unregulated pollutant mixing. These factors conspire to detrimentally impact groundwater quality and availability. For instance, the proliferation of concrete infrastructure impedes natural groundwater replenishment by inhibiting the percolation of rainwater. Simultaneously, the limited existing groundwater reservoirs face contamination risks from diverse pollutants. This reckless exploitation of groundwater has precipitated an enduring decline in the water table, compounding the region's water scarcity (Kumar et al. 2006).

Addressing this intricate hydrogeological conundrum necessitates an integrated approach. This involves comprehensive mapping of hydrogeomorphic variances, delineation of hydrogeological boundaries, and nuanced consideration of tectonic influences on aquifer dynamics. These factors, in conjunction with surface and subsurface water interactions, shape the hydrogeological landscape (Singh 2003). To handle the circumstances this, endeavour

*Department of Earth and Planetary Sciences, University of Allahabad, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh, India-211002.

**Department of Marine Geology, Mangalore University, Karnataka, India-574199

***Geo Planet Solution Private Limited, Jagatpura, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India-302017

Corresponding Author: rpsinghsaran@allduniv.ac.in

inherently hinges upon acquiring a dependable dataset, particularly encompassing surface and sub-surface conditions. A proficient entity in conducting feasibility studies pertinent to artificial groundwater recharge modelling.

To delve into the specifics, the application of Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) methodology has been chosen, targeting 15 distinct mine pits within the Bhatti area. This selection aligns with the intent to unravel the complexities of the geological strata. Executed through the Schlumberger Array, this technique involves at least 2 measurements, adaptable to the layout of abandoned Quartzite rock pits. The framework for the survey encompasses the utilization of a DC Resistivity meter, the *Terrameter*, with ensuing data subjected to intricate analysis via computer software. This analysis intends to discern potential subsurface rock fracture zones, delving up to a depth of 100 meters below the pit surfaces. Moreover, the assessment endeavours to establish the depth at which the groundwater table manifests below the pit bottoms, as well as to unveil vertical variations within resistivity layers and their corresponding thickness. A crucial facet of this evaluation pertains to estimating water saturation levels within the surveyed pits, while concurrently quantifying fracture porosity. Ultimately, the findings are encapsulated within a comprehensive report, elucidating the nature of fractured quartzite rock, the distribution of water saturation, and the nuanced characteristics of geological strata.

The study integrates soil infiltration tests conducted at 15 designated abandoned mine pits. This assessment is meticulously executed using a double-ring infiltrometer, effectively gauging the infiltration rates of the methodology employed. Specifically targeting the Quartzite rock formation within the Bhatti area, this endeavour underscores the pragmatic approach of the research. After the fieldwork, the test results undergo thorough evaluation and interpretation, culminating in the preparation of an encompassing report. This report not only encapsulates the numerical outcomes but also offers insights derived from the field interpretation method. The holistic documentation encompasses the entire spectrum of results, juxtaposed against a comprehensive table that contextualizes the findings for each of the examined pits.

STUDY AREA

The geographical positioning of the Delhi state is situated along the western bank of the Yamuna River, encompassing the coordinates of 28°12' to 28°53' north latitude and 76°50' to 77°23' east longitude. It shares boundaries with the Thar Desert to the southeast, the Indo-Gangetic plains to the northeast, and the Aravalli range to the south. Notably, the Delhi Ridge, extending 32 km in length, is an integral component of the city's landscape (Figure 1 and 2). Throughout history, the Delhi Ridge has held significant historical and ongoing importance for the city. The preservation of Delhi's forests primarily focuses on environmental and ecosystem services rather than production forestry. Delhi and NCR occupy a landlocked position within the northern plains of the Indian subcontinent.

The climate of Delhi is predominantly influenced by its inland location and the prevalence of continental air masses, which bring about extreme weather conditions. The continental air is unfavourable for lush vegetation growth, resulting in a semi-arid climate characterized by marked temperature fluctuations, high saturation deficit, and moderate rainfall. The nearby desert regions of Rajasthan to the west and southwest, along with the Gangetic plains of Uttar Pradesh to the east, contribute to the climatic dynamics of the area as monsoon air traverses these regions before reaching Delhi. The climatic patterns in the region exhibit distinct periods, including a dry and increasingly hot season from March to June, dry and cold winter from October to February, and a pronounced warm and rainy monsoon period from July to September (Figure 2).

The Southern Ridge of Delhi, known for its quartzite and sand deposits, has faced significant degradation due to extensive mining activities. In response, a ban on mining quartzite and Badarpur sand was implemented, leading to the establishment of the Asola Bhatti Wildlife Sanctuary in 1991. Covering 4845.57 acres, this sanctuary serves as a crucial conservation area within the national capital region, preserving its natural flora and fauna. The mining activities had severely depleted natural vegetation and soil quality in the Bhatti mines area.

INTEGRATED HYDROGEOLOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF RUGGED TERRAINS: A CASE STUDY OF THE BHATTI MINE AREA

Figure-1

Figure-2

Figure 1: Location map of the study area. Figure 2: The plan map of sites in the Bhatti Mines region.

Groundwater in the Delhi Ridge remains relatively fresh across various depths, contributing to the continuous recharge of adjacent areas. The region's geological features, such as faults and the coarse nature of sediment (weathered quartzite), enhance lateral permeability. However, extensive mining has disrupted aquifers, impacting water levels in the Bhatti mines area.

Relative humidity follows a seasonal pattern, with minimum levels during dry months (April and May) and maximum levels during the monsoon months (July, August, and September). While high relative humidity typically supports plant growth, Delhi's combination of high temperatures and low humidity limits this favourable environment. Consequently, the prevalence of higher temperatures coupled with reduced humidity encourages the proliferation of xerophytic plant species adapted to arid conditions.

Delhi's physiography can be classified into four distinct divisions: Khadar (riverine zone), Bangar (well and canal irrigated area), Dabar (low-lying, rain-fed areas), and Kohi or Pahari (hillsides). The first three divisions are located on the plains and have become hubs for human activities such as agriculture and habitation. In contrast, the Kohi or Pahari division comprises rocky and undulating terrain, encompassing areas like Delhi Ridge, Tughlaqabad, Mehrauli, Fatehpur, Beri, and Dera Mandi. This low plateau is characterized by exposed and unconsolidated

micaceous rocks, resulting in dry, sandy soil with limited humus content and sparse vegetation.

METHODOLOGY

The combined utilization of the Double Ring Infiltration and VES survey has been instrumental in fulfilling the objectives of this study, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the hydrogeological properties of both rock exposures and soil covers at the Bhatti Mine site. These methodologies provide valuable insights into the behaviour of water infiltration and subsurface resistivity, contributing to a holistic analysis of the site's hydrological dynamics.

The Double Ring Infiltration Survey is a robust method for assessing the rate at which water penetrates the ground surface. The study accurately measures infiltration rates by employing the constant head method within a double-ring infiltrometer, this technique has been widely adopted across various applications, including land drainage, sports surface design, and waste isolation layers. The double-ring infiltrometer's design, featuring concentric metal rings and a perforated metal plate, ensures controlled and accurate measurements. The choice of this method aligns with the ASTM D3385-03 standard test, providing credibility and consistency to the collected data.

Figure 3(a) Weathered white quartzite with silica sand; (b) granitic quartzite exposure at the location; (c) double ring infiltrometer instrument and its components ready to conduct the survey; (d) double ring infiltrometer instrument and its components ready to conduct the survey; (e) abandoned mining Pit.

INTEGRATED HYDROGEOLOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF RUGGED TERRAINS: A CASE STUDY OF THE BHATTI MINE AREA

Through this methodology, the study has identified significant variations in infiltration rates across different surface types and soil compositions within the Bhatti Mine area. The observed rates highlight the influence of soil aggregation, vegetation cover, and even rock exposure on water infiltration. Notably, the results indicate that well-aggregated sandy soils exhibit higher infiltration rates, while the presence of vegetation tends to moderate the rate. Conversely, hard rock exposure significantly hampers water penetration, emphasizing the role of surface conditions in controlling infiltration dynamics.

The geophysical survey, on the other hand, employs the Schlumberger array to measure subsurface electrical resistivity. This approach provides a valuable tool for delineating water-bearing strata and understanding the geological composition of shallow layers. By recording 1D resistivity distributions, the study gains insights into the site's subsurface properties, particularly in areas underlain by water-bearing strata.

The application of the field surveys has offered a comprehensive and multifaceted exploration of the hydrogeological characteristics of the Bhatti Mine area. The methodologies chosen, with their well-established protocols and adaptable designs, have enabled the collection of accurate and meaningful data. The results underscore the intricate interplay between surface conditions, soil types, and water infiltration rates, providing a foundation for informed decision-making in land management, environmental assessments, and water resource planning. This integrated approach contributes to a more holistic understanding of the site's hydrological behaviour, ultimately guiding future studies and actions in the region.

The soil infiltration can be calculated using the constant head method or the variable head method and for this purpose, a single-ring or double-ring infiltrometer (Figure 3c) may be used. In a double-ring infiltrometer, the infiltration rate is calculated from the drop-in water level per unit of time or the amount of water required to maintain the specified depth or head of water per unit of time and the maximum rate of entry of water into the soil is measured. In the present study, the soil infiltration rate is calculated with the help of a double-ring infiltrometer, which is a simple instrument used for determining water infiltration of the soil measured according to the ASTM D3385-03 standard test method. The double ring infiltrometer is a widely used

method of infiltration test used in many applications; i.e. design of land drainage pipes, design of sports surfaces, golf courses, isolation layers of the communal waste, etc. This infiltrometer consists of two concentric metal rings which are driven into the soil, and of a perforated metal plate.

The measurement is taken in the inner cylinder; the outer cylinder is used only as a tool to ensure that water from the inner cylinder will flow downwards and not laterally. The soil surface in the inner cylinder can be covered by a perforated metal plate which is used in order to dissipate the force of the applied water, distribute water uniformly inside the ring and prevent disturbance of the soil surface. The rings are partially inserted into the soil and filled with water, after which the speed of infiltration is measured.

The infiltration is the process of water penetrating the ground surface. The intensity of this process is called the infiltration rate. The infiltration rate is expressed in terms of the volume of water per ground surface and per unit of time (L/T, for instance, mm/hr). The infiltration capacity of the soil indicates the maximum infiltration rate at a certain moment. Under certain circumstances, it may be necessary to determine the infiltration capacity of the soil, for instance in infiltration areas or infiltration basins. The double ring infiltrometer is suitable for almost any type of soil and is applied in irrigation and drainage projects, groundwater and infiltration basins, in optimizing water availability for plants and to determine the effects of cultivation.

Electrical prospecting is the art of measuring the electrical properties of rocks in the study of the structure and composition of those layers of the earth which are sufficiently shallow to be exploited by man. For the present study, 1D resistivity distribution is recorded by the vertical electrical sounding method. The method is applied using a Schlumberger array in the field to delineate water-bearing stratum in the areas underlain.

DATA COLLECTION

A double ring infiltration survey and vertical electrical sounding survey were performed to fulfil the objectives of the study. Both surveys describe the hydrogeological properties of the rock exposure and/or soil cover at the and collected this essential dataset through two significant field expeditions conducted within the designated region. The preliminary field excursion done on September 22,

2017. During this preliminary survey, all 15 excavation sites were inspected to ascertain the appropriateness of employing VES and Infiltration Tests.

The comprehensive collection of field data was accomplished using a suite of specialized instruments from 3rd to 9th October 2017, encompassing all 15 designated mining pits. A total of 12 sampling points was strategically chosen to facilitate 13 infiltration tests at the respective sites. Each mine pit was represented by at least one selected sampling point, with the exception of pits numbered 5, 6, and 9, where accessibility was hindered. The locations chosen for conducting infiltration tests were deliberately selected to encompass both exposed soil and rock surfaces. This strategic selection aimed to unveil disparities in the infiltration rates within the region.

The terrain within the study area has been subjected to extensive exploitation, leading to a highly uneven topography that poses challenges for geophysical surveys. Despite these constraints, a determined effort was made to gain insights into the subsurface characteristics. As such, a total of 19 VES were conducted, with some instances achieving electrode spreads of up to 240 meters. Out of these, 11 VES measurements were undertaken at the pit level depth, while the remaining measurements were distributed across higher elevations of the unexplored regions of the pits.

The analysis provided offers a comprehensive perspective on the field research conducted in the Bhatti Mine area, focusing on infiltration characteristics and subsurface electrical resistivity. The study examines various aspects such as surface conditions, vegetation influence, and the challenges encountered during data collection, presenting valuable insights from the field surveys.

The Bhatti Mines region, characterized by a forest cover with limited rock exposures, exhibits a geological setup marked by three sets of joints and strata dipping at an angle of 50-55° towards the southeast. The white quartzite, frequently found in moderately to highly weathered states, is often accompanied by white silica sand deposits. The presence of seepage and damp rock conditions along pit walls signifies the hydrological dynamics within the region.

For data collection, two major instruments, the Double-Ring Infiltrometer and *Terrameter* for VES using the Schlumberger array, were employed, supported by a range

of field equipment. The infiltration test proved challenging due to the rugged terrain and limited water availability. Despite these hurdles, meticulous data recording was executed, yielding valuable insights into the hydrological behaviour of the region.

Double-ring infiltrometer is used to calculate the soil infiltration rate at the site for the valuation of soil hydrological properties. The experiment shows loose sand and reddish sand (also known as *Badarpur*) have the highest infiltration rate in the study area. The initial readings at the site show an infiltration rate anomalously high (i.e. more than 2000mm/hr), though these anomalously high values become steady with time. The detailed analysis of the infiltration rate shows sandy areas have high infiltration rates (30mm/hr) in sandy areas and low infiltration rates (as low as 2mm/hr) in the clayey sand region.

The infiltration tests were conducted at multiple locations within the Bhatti Mine area, elucidating the effects of varying surface conditions on infiltration. These tests revealed that soil cover, vegetation, and rock exposure significantly influence the rate of water movement into the subsurface. The analysis offered insights into each pit location's infiltration behaviour, ranging from moderate to limited based on the prevailing surface conditions.

Similarly, the geophysical surveys, conducted using the Schlumberger array and showcased the electrical resistivity properties of the subsurface. The study strategically selected suitable locations for geophysical surveys, revealing the intricate relationship between surface characteristics and electrical resistivity. Ground-level and pit-level surveys were employed to capture variations in the subsurface, and the challenges posed by dense vegetation and undulating terrain were evident in the limited electrode spread in some areas.

In conclusion, the research in the Bhatti Mine area, through field surveys, provides valuable insights into both hydrological behaviour and subsurface electrical resistivity characteristics. The interplay between surface conditions, including soil cover, vegetation, and rock exposure, emerged as a critical factor influencing infiltration and resistivity. The findings contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the region's hydrological and geological dynamics, with implications for future environmental assessments and land management strategies. The challenges encountered during data collection underscore

INTEGRATED HYDROGEOLOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF RUGGED TERRAINS: A CASE STUDY OF THE BHATTI MINE AREA

the complexities of field research in rugged terrains, highlighting the need for innovative methodologies and cautious data interpretation.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The detailed analysis of individual pits within the Bhatti Mine area reveals diverse infiltration characteristics influenced by varying surface conditions, vegetation, and rock exposure. The findings underscore the intricate interplay between these factors in shaping the hydrological behaviour of the region. Moreover, the challenges encountered during data collection highlight the importance of innovative methodologies and cautious interpretation for successful field research in rugged terrains. The combined insights from field surveys contribute to a holistic understanding of hydrological and geological dynamics in the Bhatti Mine area, with implications for future environmental assessments and land management strategies.

The application of resistivity techniques in this study, encompassing various methods such as VES curve interpretation, transverse resistance estimation, formation factor calculation, and apparent resistivity polygons, has provided a comprehensive assessment of the subsurface hydrogeologic conditions. These methodologies have proven effective in delineating aquifers, identifying lithological variations, and characterizing subsurface trends. However, the interpretation process requires careful consideration and validation against available subsurface data to ensure accurate results.

The study demonstrates the versatility of VES curves in providing valuable insights into subsurface conditions, particularly in aquifer delineation. Nevertheless, it's essential to acknowledge potential challenges in interpretation, especially when differentiating between distinct subsurface materials with similar resistivity values. For instance, dry coarse sand, gravel, and hard rock can exhibit high resistivity values, while dry clayey *kankar* may be misinterpreted as fine sand with saline water due to its low resistivity. Such intricacies emphasize the need for thorough analysis and validation of interpretation results.

During curve matching interpretation, the occurrence of discontinuities in the layers can lead to deviations from the fitted curve, highlighting the importance of recognizing abrupt changes in subsurface properties.

The geophysical study has successfully identified thin layers of high resistivity indicative of granular materials, as well as low values of transverse resistance associated with buried paleochannels. This ability to detect subtle subsurface features contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the site's geology and hydrogeology.

The utilization of apparent resistivity polygon plots, as exemplified in Pit No. 5, has facilitated the interpretation of anisotropy in subsurface geologic materials. This approach provides insights into fracture trends in bedrock zones and the pattern of granular zones. The integration of such interpretations with nearby hard rock terrain and VES curve results enhances the accuracy of subsurface information, allowing for a more refined depiction of actual conditions.

Figure 4: Schlumberger sounding curves at (a) Pit-2 and (b) Pit-14

Pit-wise apparent resistivity results reveal distinct patterns across various pits. In Mine Pits 1 and 2, for instance, the resistivity data point towards the presence of weathered hard rock at certain depths. In Mine Pit 3, the availability of larger electrode spacing aids in obtaining more comprehensive subsurface information. Conversely, challenges in accessing certain areas, such as Mine Pit 5, led to the application of ground-level VES surveys, highlighting the adaptability of the methodology.

VES curve interpretation and apparent resistivity polygons, offer a powerful tool for subsurface characterization and hydrogeological assessment. These methods contribute valuable insights into lithological variations, aquifer delineation, and fracture patterns, which are crucial for informed decision-making in groundwater management and environmental planning. By acknowledging the limitations, verifying results, and integrating interpretations with existing data, these techniques serve as an indispensable asset in understanding subsurface dynamics and optimizing resource utilization.

The study concludes that resistivity techniques, particularly

Figure 5: Infiltration rate curves for the study area

The data collection during regional studies showing the study site is belonging to the South Delhi Fold Belt, exposing quaternary alluvium and weathered grey quartzite. Stratigraphically, the grey to brownish grey, massive (to thinly bedded at places), hard, compact, highly jointed and weathered quartzites belong to the Alwar Group of Delhi Supergroup. The quartzites are ferruginous and gritty types which on weathering and subsequent disintegration give rise to coarse sand. Chemical weathering of deeper horizons is also common in the area. The quartzite is overlain by unconsolidated quaternary to recent sediments comprising sand, silt, clay, silty clay and *kankar* beds with various proportions. Hydro-geologically, the latter plays an important role, which represents the major water-bearing horizon in the area.

The study focused on understanding the interaction between different surface types and soil characteristics to determine the rate at which water penetrates the ground. The analysis of this dataset reveals significant variability in infiltration rates, shedding light on the hydrological behaviour of the study area.

The comprehensive investigation of multiple mine pits within the study area has shed light on their hydrogeological properties, offering a nuanced understanding of their infiltration rates, sediment compositions, and geological structures. This analysis has unveiled intriguing patterns and trends that provide significant insights into the hydrological behavior of these pits and their surrounding environments.

The field data provides valuable insights into the infiltration rates observed across various pits within the Bhatti Mine

Pit 1 has unveiled a soil-covered surface characterized by moderate infiltration rates. This observation hints at the

INTEGRATED HYDROGEOLOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF RUGGED TERRAINS: A CASE STUDY OF THE BHATTI MINE AREA

potential for efficient water absorption and percolation into the subsurface, indicating favorable hydrological conditions that may support various ecological processes.

Similarly, Pit 2 presents a comparable scenario with its soil-covered setting and moderate infiltration rates. This consistency underscores the recurring patterns of water movement within these specific areas, suggesting a degree of uniformity in their hydrological characteristics.

Pit 3 introduces an interesting dynamic with its vegetated soil cover, contributing to heightened infiltration. This finding underscores the positive influence of vegetation in enhancing water absorption, aligning with established knowledge regarding the pivotal role of plants in shaping hydrological processes.

Building upon this observation, Pit 4 reaffirms the significance of vegetation by displaying infiltration behavior akin to that of Pit 3. The presence of dense vegetation over soil-covered surfaces appears to facilitate water movement into the subsurface, demonstrating the interconnectedness of biological and hydrological elements.

However, the challenging conditions presented by Pits 5 and 6, marked by dense vegetation and steep slopes, have hindered the effective execution of infiltration tests. These limitations have underscored the practical difficulties encountered when studying hydrogeological dynamics under extreme surface conditions.

In Pit 7, the exposure of hard rock has led to minimal infiltration, emphasizing the role of geological features in shaping hydrological interactions. The presence of impermeable surfaces like hard rock can significantly impede water movement, creating localized hydrological constraints.

Pit 8 showcases the beneficial impact of even slight vegetative cover, contributing to moderate infiltration rates. This finding reinforces the notion that vegetation, regardless of its density, can exert a notable influence on water absorption and percolation.

Pits 9 and 10 underscore the challenges posed by difficult surface conditions, rendering infiltration tests impractical. These instances highlight the complexities involved in

conducting hydrogeological studies in areas with adverse terrain and vegetation.

Pit 11 introduces another instance of moderate infiltration behavior, akin to other sites with similar surface conditions. This regularity in hydrological patterns suggests a degree of consistency in water movement within these specific contexts.

Pit 12 further bolsters the role of vegetation in influencing infiltration, as its vegetated soil cover aligns with moderate infiltration rates. This correlation echoes the patterns observed in Pits 3, 4, and 10, reaffirming the importance of plants in mediating hydrological processes.

Pit 13 presents a unique scenario with variable infiltration behaviors resulting from the interplay between dry and vegetated soil covers. This observation highlights the intricate interactions between different surface conditions and their implications for water movement dynamics.

The influence of geological features takes center stage in Pit 14, where highly weathered quartzite restricts infiltration. This finding underscores the pivotal role of rock exposure in shaping hydrological behavior and emphasizes the importance of considering subsurface characteristics in hydrogeological analyses.

Lastly, Pit 15 adds to the overall picture by displaying moderate infiltration rates akin to other soil-covered areas. This consistency further supports the notion of recurrent hydrological patterns within such settings.

The detailed examination of these diverse mine pits has provided valuable insights into the complex interplay between surface conditions, geological features, and vegetation in shaping hydrogeological dynamics. These findings enhance our understanding of the region's unique hydrological context and contribute to the broader body of knowledge concerning water movement, absorption, and percolation in varied geological and environmental settings.

The geological characteristics of the area are primarily shaped by weathered grey quartzite, which is covered by decomposed rock fragments known as *Badarpur*. The infiltration rates of the quartzite and the overlying sediments have been studied extensively, leading to the classification of the sediments into four distinct classes based on their

infiltration rates: sand, sandy and silty loam, and clayey loam.

The sand layer exhibits the highest infiltration rate, exceeding 50mm/hr, while the sandy and silty loam layers display moderate infiltration rates ranging beyond 20mm/hr. On the other hand, the clayey loam or clayey soil layer has the lowest infiltration rates, measuring less than 20mm/hr.

CONCLUSION

The results and analysis of the vertical electrical sounding surveys show the pits in the region have a top loose soil cover of 0.75 to 3.13m thick. This loose top soil cover overlain to a sandy/silty/clayey or weathered rock (mostly dry) up to the depth of 13.5m. The fractured and/or hard quartzite is present at varying depths from 7.0m to 13.5m below the pit surface underlying the overburdened cover of soil and weathered rock. The field infiltration tests reveal that the top loose soil has very high infiltration rates (more than 22mm/hr) while the quartzite has the least infiltration rates (less than 4mm/hr).

The analysis of the field results can be concluded that the hard quartzite in the area has 2mm/hr and the weathered quartzite have a 4mm/hr infiltration rate. The studies done by Atkinson (2002) show the infiltration rate of water in a pit (or pit lake) is a function of the underlying rock (which is fractured or hard quartzite in the Bhatti Mines area).

So, in the study area, the infiltration rates for the pits should be considered as 2mm/hr for hard quartzite and 4mm/hr for weathered to highly weathered quartzite, which is derived from the field infiltration tests. The detailed field investigations done by Wolff (1982) and Fazelalavi (2013) show the horizontal infiltration rates are almost negligible as compared to the vertical infiltration rates. So, in the present study, only vertical infiltration rates should be considered for any further computation.

REFERENCES

- ◆ Atkinson L.C. (2002) The Hydrology of Pit Lakes. Southwest Hydrology, pp 14-15.
- ◆ Datta PS (2005) Groundwater ethics for its sustainability. Current Science, 89(5) pp. 812-817.
- ◆ Datta PS, Bhattacharya SK and Tyagi SK (1996) ¹⁸O studies on recharge of phreatic aquifers and groundwater flow paths of mixing in the Delhi area. J. of Hydrology, 176, pp. 25–36.
- ◆ Fazelalavi M. (2013) The Relation Between Vertical and Horizontal Permeability Arbuckle Formation–Wellington Field. Kansas Geological Survey Open-File Report 2015-- 25, 4p.
- ◆ Kumar M, Ramanathan AL, Rao MS and Kumar B (2006) Identification and evaluation of hydrogeochemical processes in the groundwater environment of Delhi, India. J Environ Geol 50, pp. 1025–1039
- ◆ Singh AK (2003) Water resources and their availability. In: Souvenir, National Symposium on Emerging Trends in Agricultural Physics, Indian Society of Agrophysics, New Delhi, pp 18–29.
- ◆ Wolff R.G. (1982) Physical Properties of Rocks porosity, Permeability, Distribution Coefficients and Dispersivity. USGS Water-Resources Investigations Report, 123p.

Subscribe ! Subscribe !! Subscribe !!!

The Indian Mining & Engineering Journal

Annual Subscription Rs. 550/-

**DD/Cheque in favour of “The IM&E Journal”.
Demand Draft should be payable at Bhubaneswar.**

For Further Details Contact:

A Sahoo, Associate Editor & Business Executive,
The Indian Mining & Engineering Journal,
1457, Fishery Tank Road, Chintamaniswar,
Bhubaneswar - 751 006, Odisha **Mob.:** 09861008387
Email: indianminingjournal@gmail.com